

SOFTWARE DEFINED NETWORKING BASED ON CENTRALIZED CONTROL FOR SMART GRID COMMUNICATION

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Abstract:

Communication networks are growing, and there is a need for improved planning and evolution of networks. Customers require services to be implemented in a shorter time frame. Engineers are obligated to manage several nodes and upskill themselves with various vendors' Operating System. Vendors currently dictate to the Service Provider regarding their devices' abilities, limiting the Service Provider's capability and their company's technology strategy. The same applies to the electrical distribution companies; scalability, reliability, and intelligence become requirements.

Customers and Clients assess a network on availability, reliability, control, and security. The four factors stated can be assessed on a Software Defined Network (SDN), which can be applied to an SDN Smart home, SDN Automation plant, and SDN Electrical distribution system. . This capability will allow companies to perform the following services: Gain control of the network in managing and executing, increase security on each layer, collect data to understand the network and customer's experience, troubleshoot faults effectively, and, creation of services from a centralized controller.

Keywords: Software Defined Network(SDN), Smart Grid(SG), centralized, security, Application Programmable Interface(API), analytics, automation.

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INTRODUCTION

The need for control, management, security, and intelligence to be built within networks demands technology solutions to meet the above requirements. As services on the network increase and companies become more digital, the network's devices require smart features to implement in a shorter time frame—the integration evaluates how Software Defined Networking technology is applied to the Smart Grid (SG). In recent years, Smart Grids witnessed tremendous growth in communication infrastructure. Smart Grid network requires a significant effort in terms of network management and security. The SDN+SG will develop a new target architecture to meet the

advanced needs of connectivity to the end-user. Figure 1 shows the layered approach applying SDN to SG use cases.

METHODOLOGY

For an end-to-end network solution, the capability of **Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC)** is introduced, which provides a cloud computing platform at the edge of the Radio Access Network (RAN). MEC offers storage and computational resources. Facilitating multi-service and multi-tenancy by allowing authorized 3rd parties to make use of storage and network node processing.

Figure 1: Layered approach of Software Defined Network applied to SDN Smart Home, SDN Automation Plant, and SDN Electrical Distribution

The technology concept drives the telecommunication and Smart Grid markets to deploy integrated intelligent systems. Also, MEC is a crucial enabler to support M2M and IoT services for smart city services, the energy sector, and the automotive industry. These sectors require improvements and intelligence, which Software Defined Networking offers, through its flexibility and scalability solution.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Each user case directs the evolution of technology for automation and computing. Without centralized control, the market will not be able to achieve its goals. The end goal is to enable multiple cloud providers to provision new services, connecting the customer in a smart city and smart lifestyle.

Table 1: Characteristics of MEC when applied to sectors

Characteristics of MEC	Smart Home	Smart City	Remote Surgery	Autonomous Vehicle	AR	VR	Gaming	Retail	Wearable IoT	Farming	Smart
Low Latency		x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x
Increase Bandwidth	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Content Awareness	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Fast Inter-RAT handoff	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x		
Caching	x	x			x	x	x	x	x		

Edge Analytics	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x		
security	x	x			x		x			x	x
fast mobility	x	x	x	x	x		x		x	x	x

The characteristics (Porambage, 2018 et al.) of MEC applied to the real world can benefit Smart Grid in several sectors highlighted in Table 1. The technical architecture uses Software Defined Networking has the platform to enable computing for MEC.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The design focused on simulation and a prototype of integrating SDN and SG. It consisted of three phases to reach objectives and test use cases.

The successful integration was performed using an open-source management tool to control and monitor the live environment from a GUI and configure policies from the SDN controller via OpenFlow protocol. Test phase three proved the control and intellectual ability of SDN when applied to SG. Further technical test was done to test the correlation and load balancing of the traffic between specific interfaces; the results showed a 96% GTP Correlation rate and ability to capture L2 GRE tunneling/de-capsulation.

MEC's deployment, an SDN component across a communication network and smart grid network, will enable a further scalable, efficient, and resilient network. Connecting the user closer to their lifestyle and connecting the world to the environment of automation.